

Abstract

This case study on S & R Aquafarm is to show the problems that are current and the solutions to amend the issues. The problems include the limited number of employees and a small management, and low number of sales. The case analysis that are included are cases that look into understaffing, softwares used to monitor productivity and how experience affects a workplace. The alternative solutions that are listed are referencing from the case analysis. These are introducing on-call hiring of staffs, software to monitor productivity, and providing online training. Out of these three solutions, introducing the on-call hiring of staffs was the most recommended option followed with the addition of providing online training. Having software to monitor productivity for this small company would be useless. To conclude the recommendations are viable and will improve overall performance.

Background Information

According to Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei (2020), S & R Aquafarm was founded in 2011 by Haji Suni bin Haji Sulaiman and his son Syazwan bin Haji Suni. The founders did not have any background regarding agriculture, but they are utilizing the farming method of aquaponics. Currently, Syazwan is managing and operating S & R Aquafarm alone whilst producing an average of 4 kg of produce a week. Another part of their revenue stream is selling small modular systems for home use which is essentially a fish tank with a grow bed system which can house a range of 20-60 plants and 40-100 red tilapias.

Problem Statement

S & R Aquafarm are trying to increase their productivity which in turn increases their product yield and sales. They understand that their target market is very niche as they are selling organic premium quality goods with the absence of chemical pesticides and fertilizers. With little employees and a small management, they are able to sustain but are unable to reach a desired sales amount in the market. Having said this, there are currently only Syazwan and his father who are active in harvesting the crops and collecting the fishes. Applying some forms of Digital Human Resource Management (DHRM) would help tackle this issue.

Case Analysis

Referring to this case, there are multiple issues that can be tackled. Firstly, there are very few employees to have a workforce to produce a high amount of revenue. A study done by Kendrick Callao (2017) states that being understaffed would result in lower customer satisfaction. It will also provide better productivity towards the flow of operation. Initially having more staff would prove to be costly but a positive effect on having more staffing could prove to produce more yield to cater to the market. This will increase the sales of the business as well as reputation of the business. They have looked into on-call staffing during peak seasons to ensure that costing for staff was as efficient as possible. The impact on both permanent and on-call employees showed that both were determined to work and produce results. There were disadvantages that follow through this. The staff were inexperienced, and training was needed to uphold the standards of operation. It was also difficult to guarantee that the on-call staff would report to their work as they could have prior engagements.

Secondly, there are no ways to measure the employees' productivity and their efficiency. Another case study where A-Legal was having difficulties in monitoring productivity and efficiency of their workers (A-Legal chooses Activity Monitor to measure and improve workplace productivity, 2018). They noticed there was a decline in jobs done in a specific amount of time compared to before. They implemented a software where the software was able to monitor the activities of the workers and show their productivity. This has proved great results where there was a major increase in employee productivity, improved customer service and more efficient staffing. They managed to decrease payroll costs by 20 percent to enable potential growth. This was done due to more efficient staffing whereby 4 staffs are needed instead of 5 to complete a certain task. The software also improved their revenues by having better communications with their customers. The company was able to efficiently communicate with their customers and solve issues that they were facing which significantly increased customer satisfaction and increased their ratings hence led to higher recommendation from their customers.

Lastly, the employees have no training, proficiency, or background experience regarding the job scope. A publication from the Department for Work and Pensions by the Government of UK (2013) showed benefits of retaining experienced workers as compared to hiring inexperienced workers. Companies in this publication also agreed that hiring experienced workers would be

more beneficial. The experienced workers are able to bring their knowledge from the previous corporation they have worked in and share it with the company and the company may develop or learn from it. Training could also be provided to the inexperienced workers conducted by the management in order for the standards of their operation be enforced. The result from the training would vary for the different individuals due to their varying capabilities. The training could also show the company that which staffs are more competent and that they can work on improving the less competent employees or decide to dismiss them.

Alternative solutions

One of the solutions that would prove beneficial to this company is the use of on-call staff. There are plenty of software applications in the UK where plenty of part timers register and look for part time jobs for a short period of time, usually daily. The software shows part timers available jobs and the duration of the jobs and they have to accept it. The company will pay to the application and the application will pay to the part timer after collecting a fee. This allows the company to be able to manage their staff costing efficiently and allows them to seek out potential permanent staff. The on-call staff can be called and hired during the harvesting season when the company wants to effectively collect their crops and ensure a faster delivery to the end customers. The on-call staff can also be there to help with the planting of the seeds of the crops which is very labour intensive and would take much time if it were done by only one person. Another positive effect from this is that during the growing season where there is little work, there is no need for staffing so the company will save the cost that is beared compared to having permanent staffs. This also applies to the fishery part of the business. When the fishes reach a certain size and weight, it is time to catch them and sell them. Hiring the on-call employees during this season will not only help ease the owner's tasks but will prove a more productive and efficient yield. The yield in this case can be calculated and compared by finding out how much sales they are able to make divided by the time spent into harvesting the crops and catching the fishes. With the limited number of crops and fishes, it is possible to fix the amount of sales and divide by the time spent, which is inversely proportional to the number of workers available to help.

The advantages of this solution are: -

- Allow tasks to be done in a timelier manner,

- Salary expense is maximized as compensation is based on performance,
- Possibility of experienced workers,
- Have no limit of number of available workers,
- Reduce unnecessary costs in staffing.

The disadvantages of this solution are: -

- Undependable workers as they come as they like,
- Possibility of inexperienced workers,
- Must provide training every time for new workers,
- Unpredictable schedule,
- More expensive when wage is calculated per hour.

Another solution that can be used is to implement in this situation is the use of the software which was used by A-Legal in the Case Analysis. Having a software to monitor their productivity would prove useful in incentive programs if the company were to issue any. This would increase productivity and may motivate the workers into delivery better results. This would also increase cost efficiency by penalizing the workers who do not complete the work at a given time as they are supposed to. Using the software may separate the more competent workers with the incompetent ones and make filtering through the staffs easier and to assess what improvements can be done or dismissal if necessary. Having the software would also benefit customer satisfaction as it provides a direct communication channel for improvements and complaints. Increased customer satisfaction would indirectly affect sales and reputation.

The advantages of this solution are: -

- Close monitoring with realistic productivity values,
- Separating more capable talents and retaining them,
- Decreased costs by making workload more efficient.

The disadvantages of this solution are: -

- Possibility of employees being reluctant and resistant,
- Employees feeling their privacy is invaded,

- Costly to implement due to expensive software.

The last solution for this company is having online courses and training to increase proficiency of the employees. The internet now has an abundant source of knowledge that is easily accessible. There are also courses to improve one's ability and hone their skills. For this company, there are plenty of courses that provide information regarding aquaponics. With no skills or expertise, learning the basics would prove to be time consuming. Despite being time consuming, it can also be very detailed and elaborate to help understand the methods easier. Some would prefer a quick step by step and some may appreciate the science behind it.

The advantages of this solution are: -

- Abundant information that is readily available,
- Easily accessible knowledge,
- Creditable information from relevant sources.

The disadvantages of this solution are: -

- Time consuming as of any training,
- May be too detailed and irrelevant for their level,
- May not be creditable if not from relevant sources.

Recommendations:

With all the information discussed, the optimal solution for this particular case would be implementing the first solution. Having on-call workers would benefit this company as this company relies heavily on seasons. It is unnecessary to have full time permanent staff where there are extended downtimes and have very low productivity. This would also limit the unnecessary costs and number of unnecessary labour. During harvesting seasons, produce and fishes can be sent out with the on-call workers helping. This will produce a maximum yield and thus providing a good profit. The company is able to hire as much labour for a day to complete high demands within a short period of time. The disadvantage of having unskilled and inexperienced workers would not be too much of a problem as the tasks that need to be done are simple and can be done with ease.

The second recommended solution would be the third solution discussed above. Training with the availability of unlimited information on the internet can improve the skills of the employees with their current knowledge of aquaponics. This is an added solution to the first solution and not a better substitute. These are two different techniques which can both be implemented. With the training that they learn through online, they can improve the ways of their farming and innovate more ways to increase their scale of produce and fishery. This can also be used as a research and development technique to test out the methods used online and if they are viable enough to be practical.

The last solution of using the software would prove undesirable to the company. The company is a very small scaled organization targeting a niche market hence there is no need for this extreme measure to micro-manage the staffs. Having the software is also very costly and unnecessary while the company has less than 10 employees. Hence this method should only be used after the company has decided to enlarge the scale to an approximate of 200 employees where his revenue would justify the cost of the software.

Conclusion

The problem of having little staff and low gross sales can be solved with implementing the recommended solutions. With these solutions, there should be a significant increase in overall performance. This performance includes workers' productivity, sales, and competency. The solutions that are recommended are using on-call hiring of staffs and providing online training. For on-call hiring of staffs, there are plenty of benefits where the company can limit the staffing cost over the year and have a high return during the peak seasons. For providing online training, this is advantageous towards the company to procure skilled workers which in turn increases the productivity yield as well as maintain the standards of quality.

References

- Computer Monitoring Case Study. A-Legal. (n.d.). Retrieved November 11, 2020, from <https://www.softactivity.com/case-studies/a-legal/>
- Department for Work and Pensions. (2013). *Employer case studies* [Brochure]. Department for Work and Pensions.
- Gholston, S. (2015). *Developing Strategies for Hiring Managers: A Case Study on Hiring Employees* (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University, 2015). Walden University.
- Munsamy, M., & Telukdarie, A. (2019). Digital HRM Model for Process Optimization by Adoption of Industry 4.0 Technologies. *2019 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management (IEEM)*. doi:10.1109/ieem44572.2019.8978726
- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Neelie Verlinden (2019). Back to Basics: What is Digital HR? Retrieved November 11, 2020, from <https://www.digitalhrtech.com/back-to-basics-what-is-digital-hr/>
- Rüel, Huub; Bondarouk, Tanya; Looise, Jan Kees (2004) : E-HRM: Innovation or irritation. An explorative empirical study in five large companies on web-based HRM, *Management Revue*, ISSN 1861-9916, Rainer Hampp Verlag, Mering, Vol. 15, Iss. 3, pp. 364-380
- Schinzel, U. (2014). Who Wants Digital HRM? The Example of Luxemburg. *Who Wants Digital HRM? The Example of Luxemburg*. doi:10.15341/jbe(2155-7950)/12.05.2014/018